

Research

Incidence and risk factor for intrauterine growth restriction in Chattogram District, Bangladesh: A population-based retrospective study, 2018–2019

Faiza Shareen^{1*#}; Sahin Akter¹; Sadia Nasrin²;

¹Department of Epidemiology and Biostatistics, Xiangya School of Public Health, Central South University, Changsha, Hunan, China.

²Hebei Medical University, Shijiazhuang, China.

Abstract: The aim of this research was to evaluate the incidence and risk factors for IUGR in Chattogram District, Bangladesh. The population-based retrospective study had a focus on women aged between 13 and 65 years living in Chattogram District, Bangladesh from January 2018 to December 2019. There is an urgent public health need to address IUGR in Bangladesh. The main research question was: What is the incidence and risk factor(s) related to intrauterine growth restriction in Chattogram District, Bangladesh? Firstly, the incidence of IUGR in all newborns at the Chittagong Medical College Hospital and the Red Crescent Maternity Hospital was studied. Secondly, a total of 400 IUGR cases and 400 non-IUGR controls were randomly selected in this study. A total of 800 mothers were participating in this study with a response rate of 95%. Among the case group, the proportion of asymmetrical IUGR was 72.5% (95% CI: 2.04–4.45) and of symmetrical IUGR was 27.5% (95% CI: 0.84–2.17). The research study revealed that the incidence of the total IUGR cases was found to be 72.5% and 27.5% for asymmetrical IUGR and symmetrical IUGR, respectively. The incidence of asymmetrical IUGR was found to be higher than that of symmetrical IUGR, with a P-value <0.05. The IUGR occurrence was seen during the later gestation period (3rd trimester) for asymmetrical IUGR, and during earlier gestation (1st trimester) for symmetrical IUGR. The features of malnutrition were more pronounced for asymmetrical IUGR than for symmetrical IUGR. No information was found on mixed IUGR. Sensitivity analysis showed that women who were ≥ 35 years old (AOR; 2.35, 95% CI: 1.04–5.83); unemployed (AOR; 2.47, 95% CI: 1.62–3.73); who had ≥ 3 children (AOR; 2.94, 95% CI: 1.85–4.32); who had a family history of IUGR (AOR; 2.13, 95% CI: 1.35–3.01), and who had pregnancy complications (infection intrinsic to the fetus or utero-placental insufficiency) (AOR; 1.94, 95% CI: 1.77–4.53) were more susceptible to the risk of IUGR. These factors were the most predictors of IUGR.

Keywords: Intrauterine growth restriction; Incidence; Risk factors; Antenatal care; Postnatal care; Bangladesh women

*Corresponding Author and #First Author: faizasfaria2729@gmail.com

Accepted: 30 July, 2022; **Published:** 11 August, 2022

How to cite this article: Faiza Shareen, Sahin Akter, Sadia Nasrin, (2022). Incidence and risk factor for intrauterine growth restriction in Chattogram District, Bangladesh: A population-based retrospective study, 2018–2019

North American Academic Research, 5(7), 101-122. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6983571>

Conflicts of Interest: There are no conflicts to declare.

Publisher's Note: NAAR stays neutral about jurisdictional claims in published maps/image and institutional affiliations.

Copyright: ©2022 by the authors. Author(s) are fully responsible for the text, figure, data in this manuscript submitted for possible open access publication under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

Introduction

1.1 Background

Intrauterine growth restriction (IUGR) is an important cause of fetal and neonatal morbidity and mortality [1, 2]. Next to prematurity, IUGR is the second leading cause of perinatal mortality, which is still the huge problem of developing countries [3, 4, 5]. IUGR has been defined as the velocity of fetal growth less than the normal fetus growth potential for a specific neonate or it is the failure of the fetus to achieve its growth potential [6] as per the race and gender of the fetus [3]. The “normal” neonate is the one whose birth weight is between the 10th and 90th percentile as per the gestational age, gender and race with no feature of malnutrition and growth retardation [3]. In the womb life or during the postnatal period, an infant with birth weight or birth length below the 10th percentile is known as small for gestational age (SGA) [3, 7]. Therefore, it is important to keep in mind that neonates with a birth weight less than the 10th percentile will be SGA, but not an IUGR if there are no features of malnutrition, and a neonate with a birth weight greater than the 10th percentile will be an IUGR in spite of being appropriate for gestational age (AGA), if the infants have features of malnutrition at birth [3]. Consequently, it is of great importance to examine and identify the incidence and risk factors contributing to IUGR, which would have a great impact for its effective decline and early prevention.

IUGR is a public health problem and noted to occur in approximately 8% to 10% of pregnancies [1, 8]. An IUGR applies to neonates born with clinical features of malnutrition and in-utero growth retardation, irrespective of their birth weight percentile [3]. These infants have many acute neonatal problems that include perinatal asphyxia, hypothermia, hypoglycemia, and polycythemia. The likely long-term complications that are prone to develop when IUGR infants grow up includes growth retardation, major and subtle neurodevelopmental handicaps, and developmental origin of health and disease. In this review, we will cover various antenatal and postnatal aspects of IUGR. The identification of IUGR is commonly made during the antenatal period. However, it can be detected in the newborn immediately after delivery [9, 10] by using clinical examination [11, 12, 13], anthropometry index [14], and clinical assessment of nutritional status (CAN) score [9]. Antenatal care is one major way of identification and dealing with this public health issue. According to the report of the National Collaborating Centre for Women's and Children's Health (NCC-WCH) published by the Royal College of Obstetrics and Gynecologists [7], good antenatal care needs to be evidence-based and information driven. Besides, IUGR may exist with or without antenatal care for any newborn [9]. It is therefore, important to understand the incidence and risk factors contributing to IUGR.

Increasing evidence from epidemiologic studies revealed that IUGR is the common end result of maternal, placental, fetal, genetic factors, or a combination of any of these factors [3]. Maternal smoking, advanced age, high parity and obesity are recognized maternal factors. A recent study found that neonates from pregnancies with placenta previa have a mild increase in the risk of IUGR [15]. Whereas, congenital anomalies, intrauterine growth retardation, cord complications and infections are the common fetal causes of antepartum stillbirth [16]. IUGR leads to early and late pregnancy complications, significant increase in newborn birth weight, length, and head circumference, less than the 10th percentile. IUGR fetus has approximately five to ten-fold increased risk of dying in the womb, with up to 23 to 65

stillbirths [17, 18]. In around half of the preterm stillbirths and 25% of the term, the stillbirths were growth-retarded [19]. The greatest incidence of IUGR in developing countries is multi-factorial and involves a complex collaboration between fetal, placental, and maternal factors even though the maternal factors are the most predominant causes [3, 20, 21]. Globally, it is observed that 23.8% of the newborns and approximately 30 million babies suffer from IUGR every year. With closer observation, 75% of all exposed newborns occurred in developing regions [20]. The incidence of IUGR in Malawi and Karachi was around 21% [22, 23]. Screening of neonatal adverse birth outcomes including IUGR is very important for obstetricians and perinatologists. Because its effect is associated with perinatal morbidity and mortality [1, 2, 24], birth hypoxia, impaired neurodevelopment, and a manifestation of the metabolic syndrome in adult life [17]. However, the incidence and risk factor for IUGR have barely been investigated in Chattogram District, Bangladesh. Demanding further research.

To the best of our knowledge, no previous study has been done in Bangladesh which focuses on IUGR, a significant public health issue. Thus, our study is vital to assess the incidence and factors related to fetal IUGR, especially in Chattogram District, Bangladesh. Showing the proportion and associated factors of fetal IUGR is very critical. In addition to this, early intervention could be suggested to achieve the sustainable development goal of a child's health. Hence, the study is important in Bangladesh where perinatal mortality is still very high. Besides, our study findings will be used as baseline data for clinicians to do prospective clinical research. Public health programs with an ultimate aim to decrease IUGR will also be implemented.

1.2 Research status and development trends at home and abroad

Bangladesh has one of the highest rates of IUGR globally. Bangladesh ranks fourth among the countries with the highest burden of IUGR with an SGA incidence of 30.5% [25]. IUGR is the prevailing public health concern in rural Bangladesh [26]. While a number of studies have considered IUGR as a vital public health issue in Bangladesh [3, 26, 27], evidence for its incidence and associated risk factors are unclear.

Globally, the incidence of IUGR is six times higher in developing countries when compared to that in developed countries, and this incidence can be further high in lower- and middle-income countries, as many infants are born in home with no birth records. The incidence of IUGR differs among countries, populations, and races and increases with decreasing gestational age. A large number of IUGR infants are seen in the Asian continent, which accounts for approximately 75% of all affected infants [3]. This is followed by the African and Latin American continents. In the Asian continent countries, the highest incidences for low birth weight (LBW) and IUGR-LBW are seen in decreasing order in the following countries: Bangladesh, India, Pakistan, Sri Lanka, Cambodia, Vietnam and the Philippines, Indonesia and Malaysia, Thailand, and the People's Republic of China (PRC) [3, 28].

Each year, An estimated 98% of global small for gestational age (SGA) indicating IUGR occur in low and middle-income countries [29]. Less than 5 percent of stillbirths are recorded globally [30]. Intrauterine fetal demise is the 5th leading cause of death worldwide. There is currently a limited understanding of the pathophysiology responsible for fetal demise. There are 76% reported cases of unexplained stillbirths worldwide [30, 31]. The Lancet published "The Ending Preventable Stillbirths Series Study Group" which has helped promote global public health efforts towards tackling this crucial issue. The initial goal was to reduce the stillbirth rate to less than 15/1000. This has been achieved already in many industrialized countries. However, countries in Asia and Africa still have much higher stillbirth rates attributed mainly to lack of access to healthcare providers.

Previous studies from developing countries have shown the incidence and risk factors contributing to IUGR during pregnancy [3]. A recent Stillbirth Collaborative Research Network study found that stillbirth risk factors known at the start of pregnancy, accounted for only a small fraction of stillbirth risk. In addition, they concluded that only prior stillbirth or pregnancy loss from preterm birth or fetal-growth restriction demonstrated predictive value [32]. Generally, the risk of stillbirth is higher in women with a prior unexplained stillbirth. Another study found the risk to be five times greater [33] and another study, two times greater [34]. Prior preterm birth of less than 34 weeks increases the risk of a subsequent stillbirth by three times. Consequently, the additional history of having delivered a growth-restricted fetus increases the risk of subsequent stillbirth by six times [35]. The risk of stillbirth is even greater for women who have delivered a viable, growth-restricted fetus before 32 weeks gestational age, compared to a woman with a prior stillbirth [33, 36].

Literature varies for the risk factors for IUGR. Epidemiologic studies have reported that various maternal factors such as age of the mother, inter-pregnancy interval (less than 6 months or 120 months or more), maternal health, behavioral habits, and maternal infection affect the growth of the fetus and are responsible for causing IUGR [37]. Strauss and Dietz have reported an approximately two-fold increase in the risk of IUGR with low maternal weight gain in either the second or the third trimester [38]. Hence, our study objectively seeks to investigate the incidence of IUGR in Chattogram District, Bangladesh, and to identify the key risk factors of its development.

1.3 Statement of the problem

IUGR has grown to become a major health concern, demanding urgent attention. It is therefore necessary to assess the incidence and risk factors for intrauterine growth restriction in Chattogram District, Bangladesh.

1.4 Nature of the problem

This population-based retrospective study was conducted to assess the incidence and risk factor for intrauterine growth restriction in Chattogram District, Bangladesh, for the period of October 2018 to November 2019. The current study had no harm to participants since the data was collected from hospital medical records with the consent of patients or participants.

1.5 Research questions

What is the incidence of intrauterine growth restriction in Chattogram District, Bangladesh?

How is the exposure to specific risk factor(s) associated with intrauterine growth restriction in Chattogram District, Bangladesh?

What is the significant relationship between the incidence and risk factor(s) related to intrauterine growth restriction in Chattogram District, Bangladesh?

1.6 Research hypothesis

There is a significant relationship between the risk factors (maternal, placental, fetal, genetic factors, or a combination of any of these factors) related to intrauterine growth restriction and the incidence of IUGR in Chattogram District, Bangladesh, which may be different for other countries.

1.7 General objective

To investigate the incidence and risk factor for intrauterine growth restriction in Chattogram District, Bangladesh.

1.8 Specific objectives

To evaluate the incidence of intrauterine growth restriction in Chattogram District, Bangladesh.

To investigate the risk factors for intrauterine growth restriction in Chattogram District, Bangladesh.

To study the significant relationship between the incidence and risk factors related to intrauterine growth restriction in Chattogram District, Bangladesh.

1.9 Significance of the study

This study is the first to investigate the incidence and risk factor for intrauterine growth restriction in Chattogram District, Bangladesh. The study would be a major contributing factor to fill this gap. The study will also add to the body of knowledge incorporated for finding solutions to issues concerning IUGR risk and its related factors. This research study will provide standard information that will help us understand IUGR risk and its related factors among Bangladesh women. The findings will be useful to the Ministry of Health and Social Welfare in Bangladesh and other health professionals to know the importance and effectiveness of women's attendance to ANC and PNC services which is vital for the development and growth of children.

This study will help policymakers, planners, program implementers, and higher authorities in health sectors to manage the situation and plan accordingly in educating society on the risk factors associated with IUGR. This study is significant as it can help developing countries draw lessons from Bangladesh's experiences and plan and implement suitable targeted control measures on how to prevent and reduce IUGR. Moreover, this study will help to identify gaps, and to improve engagement with pregnant and perinatal women, particularly in helping them to know the necessity to involve themselves when it comes to antenatal care in general.

Materials and methods

2.1 Study design and period

A case-control study was conducted among postpartum women who attended ANC and gave birth in the Chittagong Medical College Hospital and the Red Crescent Maternity Hospital from October 2018 to November 2019. This study aimed at evaluating the incidence and risk factors for intrauterine growth restriction in Chattogram District, Bangladesh. Hence, a case-control study design was appropriate because the design enables data to be collected on individual characteristics at the time of the study alongside information about the outcome, and differences between the two groups.

2.2 Study setting

The study was conducted at two health facilities (Chittagong Medical College Hospital and the Red Crescent Maternity Hospital) found in Chattogram District, the northern portion of the Bangladesh coast (Figure 2-1). Chattogram District is located in the Chattogram Division, southeastern Bangladesh. Chattogram District is also home to the port city of Chattogram, which is the second largest city in Bangladesh, with a population of 7.6 million. The health centers were selected by using lottery method. The two healthcare centers were selected because they are the largest and busiest healthcare facilities in Chattogram, and the leading provider of primary healthcare within the country.

2.3 Target Population

The target population for all pregnant women was first estimated. According to the estimation of the current study, $N=400*Q/P$, the estimated population sample size was 2000. Therefore, 2000 pregnant women attending ANC in outpatient department of obstetrics and gynecology (for either a routine or ultrasound appointment as part of their ANC) or admitted at either the Chittagong Medical College Hospital or the Red Crescent Maternity Hospital were observed

and analyzed for participation if they met the selection criteria. A sample of 400 IUGR cases and 400 non-IUGR were extracted from the population (Table 3-1).

Figure 2-1 Map of Chattogram District, Bangladesh

2.4 Inclusion criteria

Children with a diagnosis of IUGR prepared in accordance with the WHO diagnosis criteria (with features of malnutrition).

Children diagnosed with either asymmetrical IUGR (malnourished babies), symmetrical IUGR (hypoplastic small for date), or mixed IUGR.

Mothers whose long-term residence was Chattogram, Bangladesh.

2.5 Exclusion criteria

Children without a diagnosis of IUGR prepared in accordance with the WHO diagnosis criteria (no features of malnutrition).

Children with no IUGR.

Mothers whose long-term residence was Chattogram, Bangladesh.

2.6 Study protocol

2000 questionnaires based on Chittagong Medical College Hospital and the Red Crescent Maternity Hospital's electronic medical records (EMR) were collected from October 2018 to November 2019. The questionnaire asked for the incidence and features of intrauterine growth restriction (IUGR); sociodemographic and clinical characteristics; maternal, newborn and placental characteristics, and maternal obstetric characteristics of the surveyed mothers. The candidates who met the inclusion criteria were selected: (a) cases with a diagnosis of IUGR prepared in accordance with the WHO diagnosis criteria [3, 53] (with features of malnutrition), and controls without a diagnosis of IUGR prepared in accordance with the WHO diagnosis criteria (no features of malnutrition), (b) cases diagnosed with either asymmetrical IUGR (malnourished babies), symmetrical IUGR (hypoplastic small for date), or mixed IUGR, and controls with no IUGR, and (c) individuals whose long-term residence was Chattogram, Bangladesh. The study protocol was approved by the Ethics Committee of Central South University. 400 histologically confirmed IUGR cases and 400 non-IUGR as the controls were identified (Table 3-1). The subjects ranged in age from 17 to 46, with an average age of 35. The subjects were randomly distributed across Chattogram district, Bangladesh.

2.7 Sampling method

A total of two hospitals (Chittagong Medical College Hospital and the Red Crescent Maternity Hospital) were selected by purposeful sampling technique in Chattogram district, Bangladesh. According to the 2019 Bangladesh Demographic Health Survey report (BDHS 2019), there was a sum of 18,546 women admitted in the department of out-patients, 6,873 deliveries, 2,992 obstetric gynecology, and 7,756 antenatal care services. This was the basic information gathered from the two participating health facilities between October 2018 and November 2019. At the Chittagong Medical College Hospital, there are a total of 12 wards of which 3 in-patients wards and OPD unit, 3 maternity wards, 3 antenatal wards, 3 female wards and OPD unit, respectively, were selected by using the lottery method. Red Crescent Maternity Hospital has 4 out-patient departments, 10 in-patient departments, 13 maternity wards, and 17 antenatal wards.

2.8 Sample size

The sample size was calculated based on Schlesselman's proposed formula for estimating case-control studies' sample size. This method was used to calculate the number of sample size for each group (the case group and control group).

$$n = 2\bar{p}\bar{q}(z_{\alpha} + z_{\beta})^2 / (p_1 - p_0)^2$$

$$p_1 = \frac{p_0 RR}{1 + p_0 (RR - 1)}$$

$$\bar{p} = 0.5 \times (p_1 + p_0)$$

$$\bar{q} = 1 - \bar{p}$$

In the formula, p_1 is the exposure rate of the case group, and p_0 is the exposure rate of the control group. This study mainly studies IUGR and its risk factors. The main risk factors are defined by the exposure of maternal, placental, fetal, genetic factors, or a combination of any of these factors with IUGR. In this study, we estimated the OR (most of the

risk factors) = 2.0. The estimated averaged exposure rate of risk factors in the control group is 20%. Whereas, $\alpha = 0.05$ (bilateral), $\beta = 0.10$, and estimate the sample content n . The confidence interval (CI) will be set at 95% and the margin of error (MOE) will be 5%.

First we found p_1 :

$$p_1 = (0.2 \times 2) / (1 + 0.2 \times 1) = 0.333$$

$$\bar{p} = (0.2 + 0.333) / 2 = 0.267$$

$$\bar{q} = 1 - 0.267 = 0.733$$

Then used the above formula to find n :

$$n = 2 \times 0.267 \times 0.733 \times (1.96 + 1.282)^2 / (0.333 - 0.2)^2 = 232$$

That is, each group needs to survey 232 people.

Our sample size for the case : control groups is (400 : 400).

According to the calculation above, the minimum number of pairs sample both for the case and control is 232 in this study. Therefore, our sample size for the case : control groups (400 : 400) was enough and matches the requirement of the sample size in the case-control study.

2.9 Exposure time windows

The exposure in this study comprised of three separate timing windows: Earlier gestation (the first 13 weeks of pregnancy); Mid gestation (week 14 to week 27 of pregnancy), and Later gestation (week 28 to week 40 of pregnancy or to birth) of gestation, and the entire pregnancy.

2.10 Confounding covariates

The related potential risk factors were obtained from the hospital medical records in Chattogram District, Bangladesh. In the current analysis, the risk factors were divided into the following categories: maternal factors (maternal age, number of births, occupation/SES, and family history of IUGR); placental factors (uteroplacental insufficiency); fetal factors (sex of baby, gestational weeks, infection intrinsic to fetus); or a combination of any of these factors. Previous studies have shown that these risk factors are related to IUGR [3, 27, 35, 37].

2.11 Research instruments

This study used hospital medical records (EMR) to obtain participants and well-structured questionnaires comprising both close and open-ended questions were used for the collection of data relevant to the study.

The questionnaire was designed to assess the factors associated with IUGR, including the sociodemographic and clinical characteristics; maternal, newborn and placental characteristics, and maternal obstetric characteristics. for the participating women.

Sociodemographic and clinical variables for participating mothers included; maternal age, education status, occupational status, family income, number of children, place of delivery, marital status, residence, religion, partner's occupation, partner's education, and pregnancy complications. Some of the related factors included maternal BMI, sex of the newborn, pregnancy interval, gravidity, and ANC follow-ups during and after pregnancy.

The diagnosis of IUGR included: Antenatal scan [38-40] of head circumference, abdominal circumference, biparietal diameter, and femur length; Ponderal Index [41, 42]; and Postnatal anthropometry [43-45] of weight, length, and head circumference. These methods and indices were used for fetal and newborn assessment and their correlation with the independent risks of exposure during the different prenatal periods. The prenatal period was defined as the first day of the mother's last menstrual period to the delivery day.

2.12 Quality control

To ensure data quality, 2 days of training were given to researchers on the research procedure of data collection, including their responsibility for informed consent and completeness of interviewing each respondent. A total of 5 trained nurses and 10 BSc clinical midwives were recruited for the data collection process.

2.13 Data handling

Data was checked for completeness and validity of information by the researchers once questionnaires were obtained from participants. This was done to check for missing data, correct mistakes in order to avoid deviations and errors in the data collected. The researchers serially numbered the corrected data sheets. The checked questionnaires were kept by the researcher and ready for data processing and analysis.

2.14 Data collection procedure

A research permit was obtained from the two participating health facilities (Chittagong Medical College Hospital and the Red Crescent Maternity Hospital) prior to the data collection process. Based on the positive responses from each of the participating health institutions, the researchers collected data relevant to the study using hospital medical records and questionnaires at each of the health facilities. From the two hospitals, antenatal care records of 2,000 participants' births records were obtained from October 2018 to November 2019. Contacts of the 1,798 women were listed and contacted via telephone calls for participation in the study based on the inclusion criteria. Of the 1,798 women, only 1,366 women were reachable through telephone calls, while 432 women's phone numbers were unreachable at the time of the data collection process. 217 women who accepted the call declined to participate due to non-interest in participation in the study; while 349 women also refused to participate due to schedules with work and family activities. Moreover, a face-to-face interview was conducted for the data collection process, which took about 15 to 20 minutes to complete interviewing each respondent. Finally, a total of 800 postpartum women met the requirements and were willing to participate in the study.

2.15 Statistical analysis

IUGR was assessed using a standardized cutoff percentile for each measurement. The related factors associated with IUGR among the participants were assessed using multivariable logistic regression analysis. The association between the incidence and risk factors for IUGR was assessed by using bi-variable and multivariable logistic analyses. An odds ratio (AOR) and its 95% confidence interval (95% CI) were calculated. A P-value < 0.05 was considered to be statistically significant.

The diagnosis of IUGR included: Antenatal scan of head circumference, abdominal circumference, biparietal diameter, and femur length; Ponderal Index; and Postnatal anthropometry of weight, length, and head circumference. These methods and indices were used for fetal and newborn assessment and their correlation with the independent risks of exposure during the different prenatal periods [38-45]. The prenatal period was defined as the first day of the moth-

er's last menstrual period to the delivery day. All statistical analyses were completed using SPSS software (version 25.0, SPSS Inc., Chicago, USA).

2.16 Ethical considerations

The research protocol obtained approval from the Ethics Committee of the XiangYa School of Public Health, Central South University. In addition, permission was sought from the National Public Health Institute of Bangladesh, which in turn wrote a letter to each health facility seeking permission for data collection. A letter of introduction was also obtained from the Ministry of Health and Social Welfare, Republic of Bangladesh, and was presented to the Medical Directors of the Chittagong Medical College Hospital and the Red Crescent Maternity Hospitals, seeking permission for research to be conducted. Research permits were finally obtained from participating health facilities prior to data collection. The purposes of the study were explained to the study participants, verbal consent was also obtained from each of them, and various ethical principles such as voluntary, privacy, and withdrawal. Confidentiality of the responses was ensured throughout the research process.

2.17 Technical routes

(1) Data collection for case and control groups.

(2) Investigation on the incidence of IUGR.

(3) Case-control study to explore the influencing risk factors for IUGR during the 1st trimester, 2nd trimester, and 3rd trimester of pregnancy.

2.18 Justification of the study

This study will provide new evidence base findings on the incidence and risk factors for intrauterine growth restriction in Chattogram District, Bangladesh. Findings from this study will provide baseline information that will allow the focused interventions to address the factors influencing IUGR risk. Hence, reducing the IUGR incidence rate and its associated mortality and morbidity in Bangladesh. The findings will also help higher authorities, health care planners, and trainers to plan as well as implement strategies to enhance women's commitment and involvement in the provision of perinatal care for both pregnant women and women who have given birth.

Results

3.1 Incidence and features of intrauterine growth restriction (IUGR)

Table 3-1 shows the incidence of IUGR for cases with IUGR (n=400). The case group (Group A) had a higher proportion 290 (72.5%) of asymmetrical IUGR than of symmetrical IUGR 110 (27.5%). The incidence of asymmetrical IUGR (AOR; 3.02, 95% CI: 2.04–4.45) was found to be higher than that of symmetrical IUGR (AOR; 1.35, 95% CI: 0.84–2.17), with a P-value <0.05.

Table 3-1 Incidence and features of intrauterine growth restriction (IUGR)

CHARACTERISTICS	SYMMETRICAL IUGR	ASYMMETRICAL IUGR
Proportion	110	290
Incidence of total IUGR cases	27.5%	72.5%
Period of Insult	Earlier gestation	Later gestation
Etiology	Infection intrinsic to fetus	Utero-placental insufficiency
Antenatal scan Head circumference, Abdominal	All are proportionally reduced	Abdominal circumference-decreased Biparietal diameter, Head circumference,

circumference, Biparietal diameter and Femur length		and femur length- normal
Ponderal Index	Normal (more than 2)	Low (less than 2)
Postnatal anthropometry Weight, length and head circumfer- ence.	Reductions in all parameters	Reduction in weight Length and Head circumference- normal (Brain sparing growth)
Difference between head and chest circumference in term IUG	Less than 3 cm	More than 3 cm
Features of malnutrition	Less pronounced	More pronounced
Prognosis	Poor	Good

3.2 Sociodemographic and clinical characteristics of study participants

800 women participated in this study and a response rate of 95% was obtained. In this study, most of the women in the case group 267 (66.75%) were found to be ≥ 35 years old but only 148 (37.0%) of the women were older than 35 years in the control group. More than half 271 (67.75%) of the women in the case group were unemployed compared to 90 (22.5%) of the women in the control group. 177 (44.25%) ($p < 0.001$) of the women in the case group had given birth to more than 3 children compared to 96 (24.0%) of the women in the control group. During their pregnancy time, 271 (67.75%) of the cases had pregnancy complications compared to 127 (31.75%) of the controls. No significant differences in educational status, marital status, and partner's information were found (Table 3-2).

Table 3-2 Sociodemographic and Clinical Characteristics of study participants

Variables	Group A n (%)	Group B n (%)	P Value
Maternal age			<0.001
<35 years	133 (33.25)	252 (63.0)	
≥ 35 years	267 (66.75)	148 (37.0)	
Educational status			<0.001
No formal education	151(37.75)	132(33.0)	
Primary education	96(24.0)	107(26.75)	
Secondary education	63(15.75)	68(17.0)	
College/University	90(22.5)	93(23.25)	
Occupation status			<0.001
Unemployed	271(67.75)	90(22.5)	
Employed	98(24.5)	206(51.5)	
Government worker	31(7.75)	104(26.0)	
Family income (taka)			<0.001
1,000 taka	140(35.0)	76(19.0)	
1,001 taka - 2,600 taka	122(30.5)	98(24.5)	
2,601 taka - 5,000 taka	78(19.5)	143(35.75)	
> 5,000 taka	60(15.0)	83(20.75)	

Number of children			<0.001
1 child	114(28.5)	165(41.25)	
2 children	109(27.25)	139(34.75)	
≥3 children	177(44.25)	96(24.0)	
Place of Delivery			<0.001
Chittagong Medical College Hospital	169(42.25)	211(52.75)	
Red Crescent Maternity Hospital	231(57.75)	189(47.25)	
Marital Status			<0.001
Single	180(45.0)	132(33.0)	
Married	97(24.25)	175(43.75)	
Divorced	114(28.5)	79(19.75)	
Widowed	9(2.25)	14(3.5)	
Residence			<0.001
Rural	221(55.25)	187(46.75)	
Urban	179(44.75)	213(53.25)	
Religion			<0.001
Christianity	123(30.75)	132(33.0)	
Muslim	277(69.25)	268(67.0)	
Partner's occupation			<0.001
No partner	113(28.25)	138(34.5)	
Unemployed	125(31.25)	80(20.0)	
Self-employed	56(14.0)	34(8.5)	
Employed	68(17.0)	91(22.75)	
Government worker	38(9.5)	57(1.25)	
Partner's education			<0.001
No partner	113(28.25)	138(34.5)	
No formal education	26(6.5)	31(7.75)	
Primary	24(6.0)	36(9.0)	
Secondary	102(25.5)	93(23.25)	
College/University	135(33.75)	102(25.5)	
Pregnancy Complications			<0.001
No	129(32.25)	273(68.25)	
Yes	271(67.75)	127(31.75)	

Note: Figures in brackets are in percentages; Group A= Case group, Group B= Control group

3.3 Maternal, newborn and placental factors

Most 324 (81.0%) of the mother's heights were ≥150 cm and more than half 284 (71.0%) of their BMI was found to be ≥ 18.5 kg/m². Majority 337 (84.25%) of the newborn's weight was ≥ 2500g and most 235 (58.75%) of their placental weight was found to be ≥ 350 g. Majority 217 (54.25%) of the newborns were female (Table 3-3).

Table 3-3 Maternal, Newborn and Placental Characteristics of study participants

Characteristics	Frequency	Group A, n (%)
Height of mother		

< 150 cm	76	19.0
≥ 150 cm	324	81.0
Maternal BMI		
< 18.5 kg/m ²	116	29.0
≥ 18.5 kg/m ²	284	71.0
Weight of the newborn		
< 2500 g	63	15.75
≥ 2500 g	337	84.25
Placental weight		
< 350 g	165	41.25
≥ 350 g	235	58.75
Sex of the newborn		
Male	183	45.75
Female	217	54.25

3.4 Maternal obstetric factors

More than half 235 (58.75%) of the mother's pregnancy interval was < 24 months. Most 306 (76.5%) of the mothers delivered appropriate gestational age (AGA) babies and 294 (73.5%) of them had a family history of IUGR. The majority of the mother's hemoglobin level ≥ 8 g/dl were 397 (99.25%) and those that had no anaemia were 332 (83.0%). A large proportion 358 (89.5%) of the mothers attended ANC and more than half 228 (57.0%) of them attended < 4 ANC follow up (Table 3-4).

Table 3-4 Maternal Obstetric Characteristics of the participants

Characteristics	Frequency	Group A, n (%)
Pregnancy interval		
< 24 months	235	58.75
≥ 24 months	164	41.25
Maternal MUAC		
< 23 m	134	33.5
≥ 23 m	266	66.5
Preterm birth		
No	317	79.25
Yes	83	20.75
Gestational age		
SGA	94	23.5
AGA	306	76.5
Family history of IUGR		
No	106	26.5
Yes	294	73.5
Gravidity		
≤ 2	167	41.75
3-4	184	46.0
≥ 5	49	12.25
Hg after delivery		

< 8 g/dl	3	0.75
≥ 8 g/dl	397	99.25
Anemia		
No	332	83.0
Yes	68	17.0
Torch infection		
No	379	94.75
Yes	21	5.25
Chronic hypertension		
No	346	86.5
Yes	54	13.5
ANC follow up		
No	42	10.5
Yes	358	89.5
Total ANC		
< 4 (including no ANC follow up)	228	57.0
≥ 4	172	43.0

3.5 Related factors associated with intrauterine growth restriction (IUGR)

With regards to related factors associated with IUGR among the participants, multivariable logistic regression analysis was used since risk factors for IUGR are interrelated, and it gives more meaningful results. The maternal age, number of births, maternal occupation status, family history of IUGR, and pregnancy complications were found to be significantly associated with IUGR. Mothers ≥35 years were twice likely to deliver IUGR newborn than mothers who were below 35 years of age (AOR; 2.35, 95% CI: 1.04–5.83). Unemployed mothers were twice more likely to have experienced IUGR than those who were employed and government workers (AOR; 2.47, 95% CI: 1.62–3.73). The odds of having IUGR were 2 times higher among mothers who had ≥3 children than mothers who had 1 or 2 children (AOR; 2.94, 95% CI: 1.85–4.32). Mothers with a family history of IUGR were twice more likely to deliver IUGR newborn compared to mothers who had no history of IUGR (AOR; 2.13, 95% CI: 1.35– 3.01). Mothers who had complications during pregnancy were 2 times more likely to experience IUGR than mothers who did not have any complications during pregnancy (AOR; 1.94, 95% CI: 1.77–4.53) (Table 3-5).

Table 3-5 Related factors associated with intrauterine growth restriction (IUGR)

Variables	IUGR		COR AOR(95%CI)	
	Yes	No		
Maternal age				
<35	133	252	0.73 (0.39–1.34) (0.42–2.30)	1.01
≥35	267	148	1.74 (1.05–2.93) (1.04–5.83)	2.35
Occupation status				
Unemployed	271	90	2.35 (1.64–3.48) (1.62–3.73)	2.47

Employed	98	206	1.17 (0.78–1.67) (0.38–1.26)	0.8
Government worker	31	104	1	
Number of births				
1 child	114	165	1 1	
2 children	109	139	1.37 (0.89–2.15) (0.82–2.47)	1.37
≥3 children	177	96	3.04 (2.02–4.32) (1.85–4.32)	2.94
Family history of IUGR				
Yes	294	135	2.63 (1.84–3.79) (1.35–3.01)	2.13
No	106	265	1	
Pregnancy complications				
Yes	127	127	2.96 (1.74–4.49) (1.77–4.53)	1.94
No	129	273	1	

Discussion

4.1 Introduction

The aim of this study was to investigate the incidence and risk factors for intrauterine growth restriction in Chattogram District, Bangladesh. The population-based retrospective study done from October 2018 to November 2019 involved 800 participants in both the case and control groups. Intrauterine growth restriction is a common occurrence in obstetrics and is associated with perinatal morbidity and mortality [46]. Consequently, it is difficult to diagnose and treat IUGR during its early stages. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first study to assess the prevalence and risk factors for intrauterine growth restriction in Chattogram District, Bangladesh.

4.2 Incidence and features of intrauterine growth restriction (IUGR)

In this study, there was a significant difference in the proportion of the IUGR types in the case group (Group A). The data from our study revealed that the incidence of total asymmetrical IUGR cases was 72.5% and that of symmetrical IUGR was 27.5%. The incidence of asymmetrical IUGR (AOR; 3.02) was found to be higher than that of symmetrical IUGR (AOR; 1.35), with a P-value <0.05. Other previous studies found that 75% of all affected IUGR infants are seen in the Asian continent [47], which is similar to our findings. However, in this study, we did not include newborn deliveries that took place at home. Therefore, additional research is required to investigate the incidence of IUGR in babies born at home.

4.3 Factors associated with intrauterine growth restriction (IUGR)

In this study, there was a significant difference in the proportion of the sociodemographic variables across the two groups (Group A and Group B). There was almost equal representation in terms of educational status category, marital status, religion, and partner's information. However, maternal age, number of births, occupation status of mother (SES), family history of IUGR, and pregnancy complications were found to be significant risk predictors of intrauterine

ine growth restriction. Previous studies have found that these risk factors are associated with intrauterine growth restriction. Intercorrelated factors such as maternal age, parity, and socioeconomic status may influence pregnancy and birth outcomes [48].

Generally, maternal age was the most significant predictor variable for maternal and child health in the world. Similarly, in this study, it was one of the significant variables of intrauterine growth restriction (AOR; 2.35). This was supported by previous studies conducted in the U.S. [49] suggested that screening for IUGR is indicated in women of 35 years or older. Similar studies concluded that pregnancy at advanced maternal age (age >35 years old) is considered a risk factor for adverse maternal and perinatal outcomes [47, 50]. Lean et al. also reported that women of advanced maternal age (AMA, maternal age >35 years) were susceptible to fetal growth restriction (FGR) with OR 1.23 (95% CI 1.01–1.52) [51]. This may be because as women advance in age ≥ 35 years, their bodies undergo certain biological changes as they approach menopause. Although the exact mechanism of the association between advanced maternal age and IUGR requires further investigation.

The number of births is an important factor associated with intrauterine growth restriction. In this study, mothers who had given birth to ≥ 3 children were at risk of having IUGR newborns (AOR; 2.94). The findings of this study are similar to data from cohort studies conducted in low- and middle-income countries (LMIC) which showed higher odds of adverse SGA outcomes among parity ≥ 3 / age ≥ 35 mothers [52]. However, some studies suggested that primiparity constitutes an independent risk factor for IUGR with OR 1.62 (95% CI, 1.30–2.01) [53]. This is in line with a study done in Udaipur that concluded that primigravida was more prone to normal pregnancies [54]. The body of women undergoes chemical and biological changes during and after pregnancy, and these changes have an impact/effect on pregnancy. Some of these changes include hormonal changes that may expose the fetus to the risk of IUGR.

Occupational status is a modifiable risk factor for intrauterine growth restriction. In this study, occupational status was a variable associated with intrauterine growth restriction (AOR; 2.47). These findings were similar to those of a study done in Thiruvalla with a P-value < 0.000 [55]. A recent study done in Nepal concluded that IUGR was common in lower socioeconomic status (63.3%) [56]. Another study done in Udaipur concluded that low socioeconomic status, such as low-income level and poor living conditions, is associated with IUGR babies [57]. Peleg et al. concluded that low socioeconomic status may influence pregnancy and infant's birth weight [48]. Occupational status is often linked with socioeconomic status (SES). Women of low SES are more likely to have poor nutrition habits. Furthermore, low SES is associated with poor housing [58], poor living conditions, and lack of proper care for pregnant mothers. Kramer et al. suggested that socioeconomic disadvantage is not directly associated with fetal growth but may lead to adverse psychological, behavioral, or other environmental exposures that restrict fetal growth [59].

Family history of IUGR acts as an independent risk factor for intrauterine growth restriction. In this study, the family history of IUGR was found to be significantly associated with the occurrence of intrauterine growth restriction (AOR; 2.13). A similar case-control study conducted in Peshawar concluded that a history of Previous IUGR birth (OR=9.7, CI=3.3–18.3) is associated with intrauterine growth restriction [60]. Women who had previous experiences with IUGR newborns were more susceptible to the IUGR risk. In addition, the probability of giving birth to a baby with IUGR is very high when there are multiple IUGR occurrences among the family members.

Moreover, pregnancy complications are vital risk factors for the intrauterine growth restriction risk. In this study, mothers who experienced complications during pregnancy were found to be more susceptible to the IUGR risk (AOR; 1.94). In this study, infection intrinsic to the fetus was found to cause symmetrical IUGR, and uteroplacental insufficiency was found to be linked with asymmetrical IUGR cases. These findings are similar to those of a study done in Peshawar which concluded that there were positive associations between IUGR and placenta previa (OR=3.2, CI=1.1– 6.6) [60]. Another study highlighted that placental dysfunction was a potential mechanism for susceptibility to FGR [51]. Complications during pregnancy may impact the health of mother and fetus, and lead to stillbirth either

before or during delivery [61]. Common complications for intrauterine growth restriction are placental abnormalities and umbilical cord abnormalities. Placental insufficiency and placental malperfusion are serious pregnancy complications. Preeclampsia, hyperemesis gravidarum, heavy bleeding, or infections during pregnancy can also affect the weight of the developing baby. IUGR causes health problems for the baby and significantly increases the risk of further maternal complications and potential birth injuries which may lead to premature delivery. Increased complications in pregnancy can lead to stillbirth or health complications after childbirth.

Intrauterine growth restriction is a common pregnancy complication that increases the fetus' risk of morbidity and birth injuries. Hence, it is important to look for some treatments or remedies that may help slow or minimize the effects.

4.4 Implications of the study

One of the most relevant issues covered by this research is the determination of the incidence and risk factors that are associated with intrauterine growth restriction in Chattogram District, Bangladesh. This research contributes theoretically to the scientific community on IUGR by extending the literature on differences in the incidence of asymmetrical and symmetrical IUGR in Chattogram, Bangladesh. The findings of this study also highlight the risk predictors of intrauterine growth restriction. Maternal age and the number of births were found to be one of the key risk factors for IUGR, hence, it is important for women to consider having children when <35 years. Furthermore, the economic burden associated with low SES has an effect on IUGR. Mothers with a family history of IUGR and those who have pregnancy complications are at great risk of experiencing newborn IUGR. This study revealed that IUGR is a public health emergency that can have a catastrophic effect on the health of the newborn. This study also revealed how the lack of jobs or employment can have a toll on the mother's health and thus, exposing the newborn to IUGR risk. Lack of attendance to health care services when emergencies such as pregnancy complications like infection intrinsic to the fetus or uteroplacental insufficiency strikes, can lead to infant morbidity and mortality due to IUGR. Hence, it is important for the government of Bangladesh to provide more job opportunities in order to improve the living conditions of mothers in Chattogram. This study is also an eye-opener for public health officials to invest more in creating awareness of IUGR and its related risk factors. This will help to save lives and prevent maternal and neonatal deaths due to IUGR.

4.5 Limitation of the study

Like all other research, this research is not a randomized control trial. One of the most important limitations of this research was that it was conducted at only two hospitals in Chattogram district, Bangladesh, to make a comparison of mothers who participated in antenatal care services (ANC) during the study period. Secondly, the data for the study was searched and sorted from the hospital's medical record system, which is relatively accurate. However, some data was incomplete. There was missing information on some of the patients in the electronic medical records system for the support and analysis of our retrospective case-control study. Thirdly, reaching out to the study respondents to give out the missing information by telephone may have recall bias, which may have affected the outcome. Therefore, there is a need for further research to be conducted to incorporate some confounding factors, responses of health care providers, changes in maternal and child health policies, and changes within the medical establishment. It would also be beneficial to carry out the study across other regions with much larger sample sizes and demographics, in order to come up with relevant measures to conclusively address this menace.

Conclusion

5.1 Conclusion

This population-based retrospective study carried out in Chattogram, Bangladesh, describes the incidence and risk factors for IUGR. The study found that the incidence of asymmetrical IUGR was higher than that of symmetrical IUGR. The risk factors affecting IUGR included maternal age, number of birth, occupational status, family history of

IUGR, and pregnancy complications. Maternal age is a critical risk predictor for IUGR and should not be ignored. We found that: the older the maternal age; the more the number of births; the lower the SES; the occurrence of family history of IUGR, and the occurrence of pregnancy complications, the greater the IUGR risk.

The risk factors for intrauterine growth restriction have poor predictive value. Albu et al. suggested that fetal and neonatal mortality and morbidity, as well as adult pathologic conditions, are often associated with IUGR [62]. Regular ANC check-ups during pregnancy can help to detect intrauterine growth restriction and hence encourage its early treatment. ANC follow-ups are also essential for the prevention of IUGR. Hospitals and public health officers can promote the frequency of maternity check-ups and also improve the quality of the check-ups for IUGR prevention and control. Therefore, there is an urgent need to address the entirety of a woman's reproductive period for all reproductive health interventions. The studied factors need special attention in hospital-based settings in order to improve the perinatal outcome in IUGR babies

5.2 Academic Innovation

This study is the first to evaluate the incidence and its related risk factors for intrauterine growth restriction in Chattogram District, Bangladesh. To fill this gap, the current population-based retrospective study aimed to access the differences in the incidence of asymmetrical IUGR and symmetrical IUGR occurrence, and the related factors for IUGR among Bangladesh women. The study findings are therefore new and up-to-date and might be used in future research studies.

5.3 Recommendations

All health workers should teach women about the importance of conceiving babies at a younger age since its beneficial to the health of the mother and also the newborn. Health workers and public health officers should create awareness of how having multiple births can be a great IUGR risk factor. However, women may not be discouraged to have multiple children as long as they are provided with good perinatal care.

The government of Bangladesh should create more job opportunities for women in order to reduce the burden of IUGR risk. Health workers should also pay special attention to mothers who register as having a family history of IUGR and those that experience pregnancy complications. Pregnant women with a history of previous IUGR should be monitored closely and counseled regarding IUGR risks and their attendant morbidity. All health workers should teach pregnant and postpartum women about the importance of antenatal care attendance and the benefits it has on both the baby and the mother, for the prevention and treatment of IUGR.

Women in low economic class, high birth order, rural residence, and low educational status should be given special attention because they are at a higher IUGR risk. Pregnant mothers should be given special attention regarding ANC services. In addition, more comprehensive studies are needed in exploring the different IUGR factors affecting pregnant and postpartum women during ANC visits and how these issues can be addressed. The use of Ultrasonography, Doppler velocimetry, and other systemic approach and needful management could help to tackle IUGR.

The Ministry of Health and Social Welfare in Bangladesh should provide baseline information that will allow the focused interventions to address the factors influencing IUGR risk. Hence, reducing the IUGR incidence rate and its associated mortality and morbidity in Bangladesh. Higher authorities, health care planners, and trainers should plan as well as implement strategies to enhance women's commitment and involvement in the provision of perinatal care for both pregnant women and women who have given birth.

The dangers of IUGR and its related risk factors should be communicated comprehensively to all pregnant and postpartum women and their spouses. All pregnant and postpartum women in Bangladesh should be informed about the benefits and consequences of avoiding antenatal care visits during these periods. Pregnancy monitoring will help reduce this important public health concern. The use of maternal health services contributes to neonatal fitness outcomes, as the health of the mother and the newborn are carefully linked. As a result, there will be more healthy neonates and a decrease in the fetal and neonatal morbidity and mortality rates in the country. In addition, the early detection of IUGR followed by cesarean section will help reduce stillbirth and infant mortality rates.

Author Contributions: At first page.

Approval: All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Funding: This research received no external funding.

Institutional Review Board Statement: The study protocol was approved by the Institution Ethic Committee

Informed Consent Statement: Not applicable.

Data Availability Statement: Not applicable

Acknowledgments: Not Mentioned.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

References

1. Rooney CIF. 1992. Antenatal Care and Maternal Health. How Effective Is It? Geneva, Switzerland: Document WHO/MSM/92A, World Health Organisation.
2. Akowuah J.A, Agyei B.P, Awunyo-V.D. 2018. Determinants of antenatal healthcare utilisation by pregnant women in third trimester in Peri-Urban Ghana. 8(1).
3. Gebreyohannes Y, Ararso D, Mengistu F, Abay S, Hadis M. 2017. Improving antenatal care services utilization in Ethiopia. 8(11).
4. Ayalew T.W, Nigatu A.M. 2018. Focused antenatal care utilization and associated factors in Debre Tabor Town, northwest Ethiopia. 11:819.
5. Davie M.J.L, Brigante L, Livingstone C. 2020. Guidance for antenatal and postnatal services in the evolving COVID-19 pandemic. 12(1).
6. Basha G.W, Bella K, Telaw S. 2019. Factors affecting the utilization of a minimum of four antenatal care services in Ethiopia. 6 (13).
7. Timothy R.D.C, Chou V.B, Stegmuller A.R. 2020. Early estimates of the indirect effects of the COVID-19 pandemic on maternal and child mortality in low-income and middle-income countries. 8(10).
8. WHO. 2016. Global Health Observatory, Liberia Health System. Geneva. WHO.
9. WHO. Statement on antenatal Care January 2011, WHO/RHR/11012mja VOL 176 18 March 2002 pp153/4, guiding antenatal care ABC of Antenatal care.
10. Darmstadt G.L, Bhutta Z.A, Cousens S, Adam T, Walker N, de Bernis L. Lancet. 2005. Neonatal Survival Steering Team Evidence- Based, cost-effective interventions, how many newborn babies can we save? 365(9463).
11. United States Agency for International Development (USAID). 2014. Ending Preventable Maternal Mortality, USAID Maternal Health Vision for Action, Washington, DC: USAID.
12. Chatterjee M. 1990. Indian Women, their health and economic productivity, World Bank Discussion Paper; 109. Washington, D.C.
13. Family care International. Women deliver for development, London. 18-20 Oct 2007. Central Statistical Authority Ethiopia) and ORC Macro. Ethiopia Demographic and Health Survey 2000. Addis Ababa, Ethiopia and Calverton, Maryland, USA Central Statistics Authority and ORC Macro.

14. Central Statistical Agency (Ethiopia) and ORC Macro. Ethiopia Demographic and Health Survey 2005. Addis Ababa, Ethiopia and Calverton, Maryland, USA: Central Statistics Agency and ORC Macro. 2006, 8 (12)
15. WHO, 2007. Maternal mortality in 2005, estimates developed by WHO, UNICEF, UNFPA. 8(11).
16. Robertson T.E.D., Chou V.B, Stegmuller A.R. 2020. Early estimates of the indirect effects of the COVID-19 pandemic on maternal and child mortality in low-income and middle-income countries. 9(12).
17. Alkema L, Chou D, Hogan D, Zhang S, Moller A, Gemmill A. 2015. Global, Regional, and National Levels and Trends in Maternal Mortality between 1990 and 2015, with Scenario Based Projections to 2030. 6(13).
18. Prince T. Lamin-B, Catherine M.N. 2019. Importance of Antenatal Care, factors affecting utilization of antenatal care in Bombali District-Northern Sierra Leone.
19. Banke O.E, Banke A.O, Ameh C.A. 2017. Factors influencing utilisation of maternal health services by adolescent mothers in Low-and middle-income countries. 17(1): 65.
20. Wakanda B, Thompson P.E, Harris P. 2018. Factors affecting the utilization of antenatal care in developing tulle, Uganda. 8(11).
21. Pell C, Menaca A, Were F, Afrah N.A, Chatio S, Manda L. 2013. Factors affecting antenatal care attendance results from qualitative studies in Ghana, Kenya and Malawi. 8(1).
22. Dahiru T, Oche O.M. 2015. Determinants of antenatal care, institutional delivery and postnatal care services utilization in Nigeria. 21:321.
23. Nketiah-A. E, Senadza B, Arthur E. 2013. Determinants of utilization of antenatal care services in developing countries, recent evidence from Ghana. 4(1): 58–73.
24. Simkhada B, V Teijlingen E.R, Porter M, Simkhada P. 2018. Factors affecting the utilization of antenatal care in developing countries. 9(2).
25. Roozbeh N, Nahidi F, Hajiyani S. 2016. Barriers related to prenatal care utilization among women. 1319–1327.
26. McPake B, Witter S, Ensor T, Fustukian S, Newlands D, Martineau T, Chirwa Y. 2013. Removing financial barriers to access reproductive, maternal and newborn health services. vol. 11, no. 1, p. 46.
27. ICF, EPHI. 2019. Ethiopia Mini Demographic and Health Survey 2019, Key Indicators. Rockville, Maryland, USA.
28. Neg Q.X, Lee E.Z, Tay J.A, Arulanandam S. 2020. Impact of COVID-19 ‘circuit-breaker’ measures on emergency medical services utilisation and out-of-hospital cardiac arrest outcomes in Singapore.
29. Dorit S.K.W, Catherine C.H.P. 2020. Estimating the Potential Impact of COVID-19 on Mothers and Newborns in Low- and Middle- Income Countries. 10(1)
30. COVID-19 on Mothers and Newborns in Low- and Middle- Income Countries. 2020.
31. Heba H. Hijazi, Mohammed S. Alyahy, Sindiani, Amer M. Sinsiani, Rola S. Saqan, and Abdulhakeen M. Okour. 2018. Determinants of antenatal care attendance among women residing in highly disadvantaged communities in northern Jordan: a cross-sectional study. vol. 15, no. 1, p. 1.
32. Tamba E, Teleyon S, Padmore D, Karmoh D. 2017. Prevalence of typhoid among pregnant women attending the Eternal Love Africa hospital. 12(1).
33. Saadati N, Afshari P, Boostani H, Beheshtinasab M, Abedi P, Maraghi E. 2010. Health anxiety of pregnant women and its related factors during the pandemic of Corona virus. 10(2)
34. Kawungezi PC, Akiibua D, Aleni C. 2015. Multi-Center Study in Upcountry Areas of Uganda, attendance and utilization of antenatal care services. 5(3):132-142.
35. Magbagbeola D.D, Owoyokun K. 2010. Factors affecting the utilization of antenatal care services in Ibadan, Nigeria. 12(1).
36. Sharma M, Ying R, Tarr G, Barnabas R. 2017. Systematic review and meta-analysis of community and facility-based HIV testing to address linkage to care gaps in Sub-Saharan Africa. 528(7580): 1-26.

37. Afulani PA, Buback L, Essandoh F, Kinyua J, Kirumbi L, Cohen CR. 2019. Quality of antenatal care and associated factors in a rural county in Kenya , an assessment of service provision and experience dimensions. 4:1-16.
38. Pallikadavath S, Foss M, Stones R.W. 2004. Antenatal care provision and inequality in rural north India. 59:1147-1158.
39. Mccaw-binns A, Grenade J.L.A, Ashley D. 1995. Pergamon under-users of antenatal care, a comparison of non-attenders a n d late attenders for antenatal care with early attenders. 40 (7): 1003-1012.
40. Chmielewska B, Barratt I, Townsend R. 2018. Effects of the COVID-19 pandemic on maternal and perinatal outcomes. 8(13).
41. Dansabo M.T, Muhammad B.S. 2014. Factors affecting Health and Illness Behaviour in Nigeria. 7: 89-96.
42. Nomita C, Balwan S.D, Indra K. 2016. Determinants of antenatal care utilization in rural areas of India. Vol. 56, No. 1.
43. Esegbona-adeigbe S et'al. 2020. Impact of COVID-19 on antenatal care provision. 4(April): 4-5.
44. Lamin P.T, Norman C.M. 2019. Importance of Antenatal Care and factors Affecting Utilization of ANC in Bombali District - Northern Sierra. 9 (12):224-237.
45. Amentie M, Abera M, Abdulahi M. 2015. Utilization of Antenatal Care Services and Influencing Factors among Women of Child Bearing Age in Assosa District, Benishangul Gumuz Regional State, West Ethiopia. 15 (2).
46. Maulik DEV. 2006. Fetal growth restriction: the etiology. Clin Obstet Gynecol. 49(2):228–35.
47. Sharma, D., Shastri, S., & Sharma, P. 2016. Intrauterine growth restriction: antenatal and postnatal aspects. Clinical Medicine Insights: Pediatrics, 10, CMPed-S40070.
48. Peleg, D., Kennedy, C. M., & Hunter, S. K. 1998. Intrauterine growth restriction: identification and management. American family physician, 58(2), 453.
49. Odibo, A. O., Nelson, D., Stamilio, D. M., Sehdev, H. M., & Macones, G. A. 2006. Advanced maternal age is an independent risk factor for intrauterine growth restriction. American journal of perinatology, 23(5), 325–328.
50. Glick, I., Kadish, E., & Rottenstreich, M. 2021. Management of pregnancy in women of advanced maternal age: improving outcomes for mother and baby. International journal of women's health, 13, 751.
51. Lean, S.C., Heazell, A.E.P., Dilworth, M.R. et al. 2017. Placental Dysfunction Underlies Increased Risk of Fetal Growth Restriction and Stillbirth in Advanced Maternal Age Women. Sci Rep 7, 9677.
52. Kozuki, N., Lee, A.C., Silveira, M.F. et al. 2013. The associations of parity and maternal age with small-for-gestational-age, preterm, and neonatal and infant mortality: a meta-analysis. BMC Public Health 13, S2.
53. Ilana Shoham-Vardi, J.R. Leiberman, Gideon Kopernik. 1994. The association of primiparity with intrauterine growth retardation, European Journal of Obstetrics & Gynecology and Reproductive Biology, Volume 53, Issue 2, Pages 95-101, ISSN 0301-2115.
54. Pooja Dhabhai, et. al. 2020. Study of Parity in Normal and Intrauterine Growth Retardation(IUGR)Pregnancies. IOSR Journal of Dental and Medical Sciences (IOSR-JDMS), 19(7), 2020, pp. 37-39.
55. Thekkedathu, Valsa. 2015. Maternal and Placental Risk Factors associated with Intrauterine Growth Restriction and the Perinatal Outcomes. Journal of SAFOG. 7. 176-181. 10.5005/jp-journals-10006-1351.
56. Manandhar, T., Prashad, B., & Nath Pal, M. 2018. Risk factors for intrauterine growth restriction and its neonatal outcome. Gynecol Obstet, 8(464), 2161-0932.
57. Pooja Dhabhai and Ghanshyam Gupta. 2014. Low socioeconomic status related to Intrauterine Growth Retardation (IUGR). International Journal of Pharmaceutical Science Invention ISSN (Online): 2319 – 6718, ISSN (Print): 2319 – 670X Volume 3 Issue 12. December 2014. PP.05-06.
58. Xu, Q., Lu, C., Murithi, R. G., & Cao, L. 2021. Increase associated risk of gynaecological cancer due to long-term exposure to high concentration of atmospheric SO₂ industrial pollutant. Indoor and Built Environment, 1420326X211003655.

59. Kramer MS. 1998. Socioeconomic determinants of intrauterine growth retardation. *European Journal of Clinical Nutrition*. Jan;52 Suppl 1:S29-32; discussion S32-3. PMID: 9511017.
60. Muhammad, T., Khattak, A. A., Khan, M. A., Khan, A., & Khan, M. A. 2010. Maternal factors associated with intrauterine growth restriction. *Journal of Ayub Medical College Abbottabad*, 22(4), 64-69.
61. Bains, Ajeet. 1994. Effects of Maternal Age, Parity, and Smoking on the Risk of Stillbirth, by Elizabeth Raymond, Sven Cnattingius, and John Kiely. *Embryo Project Encyclopedia* (2021-06-18). ISSN: 1940-5030.
62. Albu, A. R., Anca, A. F., Horhoianu, V. V., & Horhoianu, I. A. 2014. Predictive factors for intrauterine growth restriction. *Journal of medicine and life*, 7(2), 165–171.

